

Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Some Organic Compounds of Magnesium with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Mixed ligand complexes of magnesium salts of salicylic acid, salicylaldehyde, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, *o*-nitrophenol and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid with nitrogen donor ligands 1,10-phenanthroline and ethylenediamine have been synthesised in absolute ethanol. A study of the far infrared region (between 604-470 cm^{-1}) is very conclusive for a *trans* structure for the magnesium complexes formed with ethylenediamine.

COMPARED to those of transition and rare-earth metals, mixed ligand complexes of magnesium with bidentate ligands are less well documented; only complexes with monodentate ligands have been reported^{1,2}. Fenton³ synthesised a few mixed complexes of magnesium salts with bidentate ligands, viz., ethylenediamine, *o*-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridyl, etc. We have extended the investigation by synthesising some new mixed ligand complexes of magnesium metal salts of salicylic acid (Sala), salicylaldehyde (SalH), 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N), 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ), *o*-nitrophenol (ONP) and 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (2H3NA) with nitrogen donor ligands 1,10-phenanthroline and ethylenediamine.

Experimental

For the different organic acid salts of magnesium, our usual method of synthesis was to take a suspension of magnesium hydroxide in absolute ethanol and to add to it the above mentioned ligands, (having replaceable protons $\text{HL}^{\oplus}$), in slight excess. The reaction was allowed to take place for 5 to 6 hr on a hot plate magnetic stirrer when magnesium hydroxide, which is insoluble in absolute ethanol, passed into solution. Coloured compounds separated out on cooling, which were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried at 90°.

To the suspension of these organic acid salts of magnesium in absolute ethanol, a saturated solution of 1,10-phenanthroline or ethylenediamine was added drop by drop in slight excess, with constant stirring. After 3 to 4 hr, the suspended salts passed into solution, which were then concentrated. On cooling, adducts of the general formula $\text{MgL}_2 \cdot n\text{en/phen}$, (where L=organic acids), separated out which were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 90°. The number of ethylenediamine/phenanthroline molecules attached was always found to be one.

The colour, transition or decomposition temperatures and analytical values of the compounds are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Different organic acid salts of magnesium: All these compounds are stable under dry condition. When exposed to atmosphere they absorb 2 molecules of water.

The infrared spectra of $\text{Mg}(\text{Sala})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex indicate that O-H is strongly hydrogen bonded. The O-H stretching band of Sala at 3240 cm^{-1} shows up as a broad peak between 3200-3040 cm^{-1} . Further, there are two humps at 2700 and 2600 cm^{-1} . The antisymmetric stretching frequency at 1660 cm^{-1} of the COO^- group in salicylic acid is shifted down to 1630 cm^{-1} .

In the compound with salicylaldehyde, the C=O frequency at 1630 cm^{-1} is much lower than that observed for free salicylaldehyde (1700 cm^{-1}).

In magnesium-*o*-nitrophenolate, the antisymmetric (1510 cm^{-1}) and symmetric (1333 cm^{-1}) stretching frequency of the nitro group of ONP is shifted to 1520 cm^{-1} and 1315 cm^{-1} , respectively, suggesting association of the NO_2 group in the magnesium compound.

There is a broad absorption at 3300-3000 cm^{-1} with a hump at 3040 cm^{-1} in the 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic compound. Moreover, there is another broad peak at 2700 cm^{-1} , which indicates that there is strong hydrogen bonding in the compound. The C=O peak at 150 cm^{-1} of the acid is observed at 1620 cm^{-1} in the magnesium compound.

Complexes formed with the above salts: The complexes formed by these different organic acid salts of magnesium with 1,10-phenanthroline or ethylenediamine are stable when stored dry. The transition or decomposition temperatures of these adducts are much higher than the melting/boiling

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	Transition (t°C) or decomp. (d°C) temp.	Calcd.(%)				Found(%)			
			O	H	N	M	O	H	N	M
Mg(SalA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	White	298d	52.14	4.34		7.45	51.78	4.19		7.16
Mg(SalA) ₂ .phen	White	285d	65.27	3.76	5.85	5.02	64.82	3.52	5.53	4.86
Mg(SalA) ₂ .en	Dirty white	172t & 240d	53.63	5.02	7.82	6.40	52.95	4.74	7.43	6.32
Mg(SalH) ₂	Pale yellow	315d	63.15	3.75		9.02	62.76	3.48		8.76
Mg(SalH) ₂ .phen	Pale yellow	240d	69.95	4.03	6.29	5.38	69.43	3.86	5.86	5.02
Mg(SalH) ₂ .en	Yellow	168t	58.89	5.52	8.58	7.36	58.27	5.23	7.97	6.83
Mg(1N2N) ₂	Green	300d	65.21	3.26	7.60	6.52	64.68	3.09	7.31	6.15
Mg(1N2N) ₂ .phen	Light green	250d	70.07	3.64	10.21	4.37	69.87	3.62	9.26	3.79
Mg(1N2N) ₂ .en	Brownish green	166t	61.68	4.67	13.08	5.60	60.79	4.18	12.54	5.12
Mg(ONP) ₂	Orange	180d	49.00	2.66	9.33	8.00	47.64	2.41	8.92	7.64
Mg(ONP) ₂ .phen	Orange	160t	60.00	3.33	11.66	5.00	59.62	3.12	11.23	4.86
Mg(2H3NA) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dirty white	295d	60.82	4.14		5.53	60.13	3.92		5.37
Mg(2H3NA) ₂ .phen	White	252d	70.58	3.80	4.84	4.15	69.87	3.62	4.26	3.79
Mg(2H3NA) ₂ .en	Light green	162t	62.88	4.80	6.11	5.24	62.24	4.42	5.67	4.92
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .phen	Yellow	240d	73.17	4.06	11.38	4.87	72.48	3.91	10.73	4.32
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .en	Pale yellow	150t	64.51	5.37	15.05	6.45	63.65	5.00	14.82	6.21

points of the corresponding ligands showing the greater stability. That these adducts are genuine complexes and not stoichiometric mixtures, is clear from the fact that organic salts of magnesium, which remain in suspension in absolute ethanol, passes into solution on addition of the second ligand i.e. 1,10-phen or en and the adducts then separate out from the above ethanolic solution.

In all the magnesium complexes formed with 1,10-phenanthroline, the corresponding *phen* absorptions are there, but none have been found to be metal sensitive.

The blue shift in the NH₂ stretching vibrations in the 3340 to 3250 cm⁻¹ region clearly shows that *en* is coordinated to the metal. As regards conformation of *en* in these complexes, multiplicity of certain infrared bands have been used as the criteria.

One broad band is observed at 1600 cm⁻¹ region in all these complexes; only Mg(2H3NA)₂.en shows two at 1605 and 1624 cm⁻¹. The Mg(SalH)₂.en and Mg(1N2N)₂.en show only one band at 1100 cm⁻¹ and 1132 cm⁻¹, respectively, whereas Mg(SalA)₂.en has two in that region at 1090 and 1135 cm⁻¹. The *cis*-complex usually shows four bands in that region.

Moreover, the bands observed in far infrared region (between 604-470 cm⁻¹) are very conclusive for a *trans* structure (Table 2) for all these magnesium

 TABLE 2—SELECTED NH₂ BANDS (cm⁻¹) IN THE FAR INFRARED REGION

Mg(SalA) ₂ .en	470	500	515
Mg(SalH) ₂ .en	520	535	555
Mg(1N2N) ₂ .en	515	530	560
Mg(2H3NA) ₂ .en	510	542	552

complexes. In conformity with the observations that *trans* complexes of *en* show three bands between 604-470 cm⁻¹, all these magnesium complexes have three bands in that region. Further, the pattern of distribution of the bands is also even in that region. For a *cis*-isomer, one expects four or more in that region and the pattern is three (or more) clustered together, and one farther removed. As such, a *trans-en* polymeric structure can be suggested for all these complexes.

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